

Determining Some Biochemical Parameters and Screening for Hepatitis B and C in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease in Tikrit City

Duaa A. Alayadi ✉

Iraqi Ministry of Education, Salahuddin Directorate, Tikrit, Iraq

Noura B. Abdulrahman

Biology Department, College of Science, Tikrit University, Iraq

Ahmed N. Al-Nasseri

Animal Production Department, Agriculture college, Tikrit University, Iraq

Abstract

Chronic renal failure is a life-threatening disease. This study aimed to examine some biochemical and hematological variables and liver C virus B and C in renal failure patients undergoing hemodialysis and compare these results with healthy individuals after ensuring their safety. The results of the study were statistically analyzed using SAS. The results of this study showed significant differences and an increase in each of urea, creatinine and blood sugar compared to the healthy control group. As for the parathyroid hormone, there was a clear increase and a decrease in each of calcium and vitamin D3 and an increase in phosphorus. The blood indicators of chronic renal failure patients showed a decrease in each of hemoglobin, packed cell volume, platelets and iron levels in both males and females compared to the control group. As for liver functions in renal failure patients, the results showed an increase in each of GOT, GPT and ALP and a significant decrease in each of total serum protein and albumin. When investigating hepatitis C and B viruses, this study showed the presence of hepatitis B virus in 20% in chronic renal failure patients. The incidence of hepatitis viruses in patients with chronic renal failure was 13%, and no hepatitis viruses were found in the healthy control group.

Introduction

Kidney failure can be defined in more than one way. It is a disease in which the kidneys are unable to remove metabolic and vital products from the blood and do not regulate the level of acidity and extracellular fluid and oxidation [1]. It is the end stage of kidney disease (ESKD), where the kidneys lose their vital function partially or completely due to the development of chronic kidney disease (CKD) to an advanced stage. Kidney failure can be acute or chronic. During kidney failure, the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) this is manifested by abnormal albumin secretion or decreased kidney activity [2]. Chronic renal failure is an incurable disease with high rates of mortality and morbidity [3]. At the beginning of the disease, acute kidney failure is sudden and often reversible and can be controlled if detected early and treated quickly and correctly. Chronic kidney failure is the last stage of

kidney damage and is irreversible and occurs gradually over years and not suddenly [1]. The most important public health issues is Chronic renal failure (CRF) [4], as there are clear and increasing recognitions of this problem. [5]. Global data from international registries indicates that the number of people suffering from renal failure is rising quickly [6]. The overall mortality rate is significant, and kidney failure is still common [2]. The incidence of kidney failure varies widely and differences depend on health care systems. This disease affects approximately 840 million people worldwide [7]. It is the third most prevalent non-communicable disease in the world. According to statistics from the Iraqi Renal Registry, there are approximately 200,000 people in Iraq suffering from various symptoms of kidney failure. [8]. In China, There are about 2.9 million and the mortality rate among dialysis patients was 28.42 per thousand years

More Information

How to cite this article: Alayadi DA, Abdulrahman NB, Al-Nasseri AN. Determining Some Biochemical Parameters and Screening for Hepatitis B and C in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease in Tikrit City. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2024;2(6):12-24.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(6).02

Keywords:

Renal failure,
CKD,
Hepatitis,
PTH,
Anemia,
urea,
creatinine.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

[9]. There were 720,000 patients with this disease in the United States in 2016, and the mortality rate for all dialysis patients is about 0.5% [10]. End-stage renal disease is a medical condition that requires kidney replacement therapy to maintain life. Dialysis is one of the treatments for kidney failure, the other two being kidney transplantation and peritoneal dialysis, which is a procedure that takes place outside the body and can be performed using a dialysis machine through the blood vessels. It removes waste products from the body such as creatinine, excess fluid, and urea, as well as correcting acid-base disorders and electrolyte imbalances. [11]

The excretion of metabolic waste products is one of the basic functions of the kidneys, which maintains homeostasis within the body. The most important and last waste product of protein and nitrogen metabolism is urea [12]. Uremia syndrome or urine in the blood is a metabolic abnormality due to kidney dysfunction and high urea [13]. Regardless of hydration levels, the kidneys typically eliminate creatinine, a byproduct of creatine breakdown, at a steady rate [14]. Creatinine is therefore a perfect internal standard molecule to be used in the calibration of other urine indicators [15]. An increase in serum urea beyond serum creatinine leads to an increase in serum urea. Over the past decade, serum urea levels have been strongly associated with poor clinical outcomes in various population settings, such as acute and chronic kidney injury and renal failure [13]. Numerous studies suggest that elevated levels of urea and creatinine in the serum of patients suffering from kidney failure are among the leading causes of death among dialysis patients [16,17]. Creatinine levels are good markers for kidney damage from some medicines [18,19] and surgical operations, as well as for the early detection of acute muscle loss [20]. Furthermore, the urine albumin-to-creatinine ratio (ACR) and the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), which are clinical indicators of kidney damage linked to reduced kidney function, such as chronic kidney disease (CKD), are determined by creatinine levels. With a direct link to 1.2 million fatalities, 19 million disability-adjusted life years, and 18 million life years lost, chronic kidney disease (CKD) represents a substantial global burden [21].

Diabetics and renal failure patients undergoing hemodialysis are clinically complex and suffer from a high burden of comorbidities and medications [22, 23]. Glycemic control in ESRD patients is particularly challenging because of problems with peripheral glucose clearance due to decreased insulin clearance and uremia, which leads to an underlying mild inflammatory state, which may predispose patients to hyperglycemia. Suboptimal glycemic control can lead to wide-ranging glycemic changes that ultimately lead to acute hypoglycemic crises such as hyperglycemic

hyperosmolar state (HHS). These acute complications lead to morbidity and can be fatal [23, 24].

A rare condition called chronic hyperparathyroidism (HPT) causes low calcium levels because the parathyroid hormone (PTH) is released too much and in the wrong places [25, 26, 27]. HPT is one of the complications of renal failure. Liu et al. [28] have been steadily studying the link between low serum vitamin D, low phosphatemia, low calciumemia, and high parathyroidism in people with chronic kidney disease-mineral and bone disorder (CKD-MBD). Renal failure hinders vitamin D production in the kidneys due to the crucial role of parathyroid hormone in activating the enzyme 1-alpha hydroxylase, which converts 25-hydroxyvitamin D to 1,25-hydroxyvitamin D. Vitamin D insufficiency consequently results in hyperparathyroidism, secondary hyperparathyroidism, reduced calcium absorption in the gastrointestinal system, and parathyroid gland hyperplasia [29].

One of the major side effects of chronic renal failure is anemia. Anemia occurs when the kidneys fail to produce erythropoietin, the primary hormone needed for hemoglobin synthesis [30]. Clinical signs of anemia include increased risk of cardiovascular disease, cognitive decline, and decreased quality of life [31]

Some liver enzymes and liver function tests are used to track and monitor patients. These tests include aspartate aminotransferase (GOT), glutamic pyruvic transaminase (GPT), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), total protein, and albumin. Decreased kidney function and abnormal glomerular filtration rate (GFR) are hallmarks of chronic kidney disease (CKD) patients [32]. In patients with CKD, liver function, especially liver enzymes, should be monitored to detect any concurrent liver disease. A condition known as renal skeletal dysplasia can develop in patients with CKD. This condition is characterized by abnormally high levels of alkaline phosphatase in the bones [33]. If CKD patients are not given renal replacement therapy (RRT), they will die from fluid, electrolyte, and waste accumulation. Both dialysis and kidney transplantation fall under RRT [34]. Renal bone dysplasia is associated with increased ALP enzymes in bone, which in turn can cause elevated serum ALP levels in individuals with chronic renal failure [35].

The death toll from viral hepatitis jumped from tenth or twelfth place in 1990 to seventh place in 2013 [36], making it a serious worldwide health concern. Due to a decrease in cellular immunity, hemodialysis (HD) has a deleterious effect on the immune system of individuals suffering from chronic renal failure (CRF). Patients with this condition will undergo a plethora of physiological changes that influence the activity of white blood cells, white blood cells, monocytes, and natural killer cells [37]. T cell phosphorylation pathway inhibition and decreased proliferation are additional side effects of

dialysis treatment [38]. Hepatitis B and C viruses, as well as other blood-borne diseases, are more common in patients receiving hemodialysis (HD) because their immune systems are weaker than those of healthy people [39]. Liver inflammation caused by this virus, either alone or in conjunction with other infections, can develop into cirrhosis and, in the worst case scenario, hepatocellular carcinoma [40]. Hepatitis B virus infection rates in dialysis centers differ throughout countries. It varies between 1.2% and 6.6% in developed nations and 1.3% to 14.6% in poor nations [8]. Hepatitis C virus infection rates vary widely across industrialized and developing nations, with the former experiencing rates of 4.7% to 41.9% and the latter 1.4% to 28.3% [41].

This study aims: to clarify the relationship between renal failure and dialysis patients with biochemical indicators such as urea, creatinine, blood sugar, total protein, liver functions (GOT, GPT, ALP), hematologic variables (Pcv, Hb%, platelet), iron, parathyroid hormone, calcium levels, phosphate and vitamin D, in addition to screening for hepatitis B and C and compared with control groups.

Materials and Methods

Study setting

The study was conducted in Salahuddin General Hospital, Department of Artificial Kidney in Tikrit, Iraq.

Study population

The disease was diagnosed with renal failure for both sexes based on medical history, clinical examination, and renal function tests. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study. The study samples consisted of 150 patients (75 males and 75 females) and a control group of 50 healthy individuals without signs of the disease (25 males and 25 females) aged between (20 - 80) years.

Data and collection

The disease was diagnosed with renal failure for both sexes based on medical history, clinical examination, and renal function tests. The study samples consisted of 150 patients (75 males and 75 females) and a control group of 50 healthy individuals without signs of the disease (25 males and 25 females) aged between (20 - 80) years. Blood samples were collected by

venipuncture using a 5 ml syringe from each patient with renal failure, part of it was placed in an EDTA tube and the remaining samples were placed in sterile test tubes for 30 minutes at room temperature. Then they were centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes, then the clot was removed and the rest was centrifuged again at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, and biochemical tests such as blood urea and serum creatinine were measured by DiaLab automatic analyzer (Australia). Vitamin D3, iron and parathyroid hormone were measured according to the approved device from fluorecare (China). Hematological parameters, hemoglobin concentration, packed cell volume and platelet retention time were measured using 3 NG automatic analyzer (Germany). Hepatitis B and C were detected by ELISA BioTek. (USA).

Study location and duration

This study was conducted from September 2023 to November 2023 on patients in the artificial kidney department of Salahuddin General Teaching Hospital.

Statistics

The results of the experiment were statistically analyzed using the completely randomized design (CRD) and the general linear model within the ready statistical program to study the levels of urea, creatinine, glucose, parathyroid hormone, calcium, vitamin D3, po4, platelet, iron, GOT, GPT, ALP, total protein and albumin in chronic kidney disease patients and control group. Duncan's test was used to determine the significant differences between the means of the factors affecting the characteristics. The study was studied at a significant level (p<0.05).

Results

As shown in table 1 and figure 1. The level of urea showed a highly significant (p ≤ 0.05) increase in patients (165.120 ± 46.551 mg/dL) in renal failure patients undergoing hemodialysis compared to the control group (29.500 ± 6.734). Creatinine level showed a highly significant increase (p ≤ 0.05) in patients with renal failure (9.124± 7.811 mg/dl) in comparison with the control group (0.934± 0.161 mg/dl). The blood glucose was increase (149.646±56.25 mg/dL) in hemodialysis patients in compared with control group (86.220±10.46 mg/dL).

Table 1: Comparison of Mean Values of Urea, Creatinine and Glucose in Patients with CKD and Control Group

Groups	Patients	Control
	n=150	n=50
Variables	Mean ± S.D	Mean ± S.D
Urea mg/dL	165.120±0.637*	29.500± 6.734
Creatinine levels mg/dL	9.124± 7.811*	0.934± 0.161
Glucose levels mg/dL	149.646±56.25*	86.220±10.46

Note: *Significant at P≤0.05, n=Number of cases, S.D = standard deviation

Figure 1: Comparison of Mean Values of Urea, Creatinine and Glucose in Patients with CKD and Control Group

As described in table 2 and figure 2 the level of parathyroid hormone PTH showed a highly significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in patients with renal failure (203.011 ± 183.619 pg/ml) in comparison with controls (31.318 ± 13.958 pg/ml). The present study showed a statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) decrease in calcium level in patients with renal failure (8.118 ± 1.415 mg/dL) compared to controls (9.726 ± 0.420 mg/dL). The

present study showed a significant decrease in vitamin D3 levels ($p \leq 0.05$) in renal failure patients (12.072 ± 5.619 mg/dL) compared to the control group (62.708 ± 12.819 mg/dL). Phosphorus po_4 level was highly significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in patients with CKD (6.412 ± 7.783 mg/dl) in comparison with control group (3.356 ± 0.573 mg/dl)

Table 2: Comparison of Mean Values of PTH, Calcium, D3, PO4 in Patients with CKD and Control Group

Groups	Patients	Control
	n=150	n=50
Variables	Mean \pm S.D	Mean \pm S.D
PTH pg/ml	203.011\pm183.619**	31.318\pm13.958
Ca mg/dL	8.118\pm1.415*	9.726\pm0.420
D3 ng/mL	12.072\pm5.619**	62.708\pm12.819
PO4 mg/dL	6.412\pm7.783*	3.356\pm0.573

Figure 2: Comparison of Mean Values of PTH, Calcium, D3, PO4 in Patients with CKD and Control Group

The result in table (3) which is appeared a highly significant decrease ($p \leq 0.05$) in level of Hb% in male (7.736 ± 1.415), Hb% in female (7.057 ± 1.259), PCV in male (26.281 ± 4.63), PCV in female (24.028 ± 4.262), platelet (116.400 ± 26.113) and iron (26.278 ± 39.020) in

patients with CRF as compared with the control group Hb% in male (16.024 ± 0.790), Hb% in female (13.400 ± 1.126), PCV in male (45.168 ± 2.355), PCV in female (40.152 ± 3.275), platelet (271.180 ± 89.781) and iron (105.740 ± 32.816)

Table 3: Comparison of Mean Values of Hb%, PCV, Platelet and Iron in Patients with CKD and Control Group

Groups Variables	Patients		Control	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
	n=75	n=75	n=25	n=25
	Mean ± S.D		Mean ± S.D	
Hb%	7.736±1.415	7.057±1.259*	16.024±0.790	13.400±1.126
PCV	26.281±4.63	24.028±4.262*	45.168±2.355	40.152±3.275
Platelet	116.400±26.113*		271.180±89.781	
Iron µg\dl	26.278±39.020*		105.740±32.816	

In this study, serum levels of liver enzymes: aspartate aminotransferase (GOT), glutamic pyruvic transaminase (GPT), and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) (28.666 ± 29.452 U/L, 34.062 ± 40.070 U/L, 212.666 ±

226.48 U/L) were statistically significant in patients with chronic liver failure compared to controls (9.912 ± 9.061 U/L, 9.646 ± 9.662 U/L, 70.320 ± 13.969 U/L). (see table 4).

Table 4: Comparison of Mean Values of GOT, GPT, ALP, Total Protein and Albumin in Patients with CKD and Control Group

Groups Variables	Patients		Control	
	n=150		n=50	
	Mean ± S.D		Mean ± S.D	
GOT U\L	28.666±29.452*		9.912±9.061	
GPT U\L	34.062±40.070*		9.646±9.662	
ALP U\L	212.666±226.489*		70.320±13.969	
Total protein levels g/dL	5.893± 1.135*		8.022± 0.651	
Albumin levels g/Dl	4.02± 0.645*		4.71± 0.424	

The current results showed that hepatitis B virus HBV was present in 20% of kidney failure patients undergoing dialysis (30 patients out of 150), while the control group did not show any hepatitis B virus

infection. Hepatitis C virus was present in 13% (20 out of 150), and the control group did not show any hepatitis C virus HCV infection. Only 2 respondents (1.3%) are positive for both HBV and HCV.

Table 5: Percentages of Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAg), Hepatitis c Virus Antibody (HCV) and Co-Infection in Patients CKD and Control Group

Hepatitis infection Type	Patients of CKD				Control			
	Positive		Negative		Positive		Negative	
	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%
Hepatitis B surface Antigen (HBV)	30	20%	120	80%	0	0%	50	100%
Hepatitis c virus antibody (HCV)	20	13%	130	87%	0	0%	50	100%
Co-infection HBV+HCV	2	1.3%	148	98.7%	0	0%	50	100%

Discussion

Renal function is crucial in the elimination of waste products and poisons, including creatinine, urea, and uric acid. Furthermore, they control the levels of electrolytes and osmolality in both the blood and extracellular fluid, and synthesise hormones like vitamin D, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D, erythropoietin, and renin. The nephron is the functional unit of the kidney, which consists of the glomerulus, proximal and distal tubules, and the collecting duct. Continuous monitoring of renal function is very important in the treatment of

patients with renal failure or diseases that affect renal function, monitoring the kidney's response to therapy, and determining the progression of the disease. According to the National Institutes of Health, the prevalence of chronic kidney disease (CKD) is approximately 14% worldwide [42, 43, 44, 45]. The result of the current study showed an increase in urea level in patients with renal failure compared to the control group and is consistent with [46]. This result is similar to another study that showed an increase in urea. [47]. There is another result that aligns with the

findings of the current study [48]. Blood urea nitrogen (BUN), a waste product of protein metabolism, is the metabolism of amino acids in the liver, which produces toxic ammonia, which can be converted into non-toxic ammonia, and is also a manifestation of the liver's detoxification function. BUN in the serum is usually filtered through the glomeruli and excreted from the body [49]. The kidneys eliminate urea from the body, resulting in a direct correlation between the concentration of blood urea nitrogen and the renal excretory capacity. Chronic renal failure is characterized by the kidneys' inability to eliminate urea, resulting in an elevation of its content in the bloodstream [48]. Renal injury causes the obstruction of urea excretion, leading to tubular necrosis and diminished filtration capacity. Pharmacological substances can potentially cause renal injury. The dehydration resulting from chronic renal failure also affects the urea level by reducing the renal excretion rate, thereby indirectly increasing it [50]. Filtration excretes urea, a by-product of protein metabolism, from the body, which the kidneys then reabsorb. Therefore, apart from compromised renal function, elevated protein consumption and reduced urea distribution volume contribute to elevated urea levels [51]. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) causes a cycle that keeps going by encouraging the retention of urea, which is harmful right away and a source of carbamate chemicals. These compounds then induce carbamylation, which in turn promotes inflammation. Although the metabolic production of urea may seem straightforward as it is the last product of amino acid metabolism, the gastrointestinal tract is essential for the breakdown of proteins that serve as the source of urea and the production of ammonia [47].

This study is similar to the results of another study [52]. There are other studies that support the results of this research, as they have shown increases in creatinine levels in kidney failure patients undergoing dialysis [53]. Elevated levels of creatinine result from reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and metabolism of nucleic acids and proteins. Typically, the glomerulus filters creatinine produced from phosphocreatine catabolism in muscle. However, in cases of chronic renal failure, creatinine levels rise in an inverse correlation with glomerular filtration rate (GFR) [54]. In patients with chronic renal failure, creatinine levels are elevated due to decreased levels of creatinine breakdown, renal excretion, and tubular secretion. Urea levels exceed creatinine levels because urea is reabsorbed, but creatinine is not. Therefore, when kidney function declines, creatinine clearance decreases. Serum creatinine is inversely related to glomerular filtration and creatinine clearance. Therefore, even a small reduction in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and creatinine clearance results in

an increase in creatinine concentration [55]. Many medical professionals and scientists believe that blood creatinine is endogenous blood creatinine produced in muscles after a series of metabolic changes and reactions. Creatine is produced in muscles through a series of reactions, and then converted into blood creatinine after a series of irreversible non-enzymatic reactions in muscles, and then released into the blood and excreted from the body through urine. Therefore, there is a direct relationship between creatinine production and muscle mass, and diet does not easily affect creatinine production. In the renal tubules, creatinine, a tiny molecule, is not reabsorbed after being filtered via the glomeruli. Hence, the quantitative measurement of serum creatinine eliminated through urine remains unaffected irrespective of the daily urine output [10,56].

Blood sugar levels in chronic kidney disease were high. According to [57], haemodialysis patients have higher blood glucose levels than the control group. High glucose levels have a negative effect on the glomeruli and damage them. This high glucose is associated with high albumin levels in the urine, which disrupts kidney function. In Iraq, the prevalence of hypertension and diabetes are considered major risk factors for end-stage renal disease, accounting for 40.4 % and 10.4 % , respectively [58]. The main cause of chronic renal failure (CRF) is diabetic nephropathy, which is attributed to increased glomerular flow (hyper perfusion). Additionally, hypertrophic changes associated with elevated blood glucose in diabetic nephropathy are supported by the findings of [59, 60], which align with current results. Furthermore, these findings are consistent with numerous studies, including, which elucidate the relationship between high blood glucose and chronic renal failure, as well as the impact of glucose and micro-albuminuria on glomerular damage [61].

Parathyroid hormone levels were elevated in patients with renal failure compared to healthy controls, and these results are consistent with [62, 63, 64] and parathyroid hormone has been shown to be a marker of renal failure and is frequently examined for follow-up [65].

Calcium levels were shown to be decreased in the current study and this result is close to another study [66-73] which showed ($P < 0.0001$) a decrease in calcium level in patients (8.06 ± 0.18 mg/dL) compared to the control group (10.15 ± 0.23 mg/dL). Also, a study by [63] showed that 55.7% of CKD patients showed calcium imbalance, and there are studies consistent with our study that showed decreased calcium levels. [67, 68] The current results indicated a decrease in vitamin D3 compared to the healthy group and are consistent with previous research that reported decreased vitamin D3 level in individuals with kidney

failure [69 31]. Similarly, another study found that the D3 level in patients with renal failure (11.98 ± 0.79 mg/dL) was lower than that in the control group (20.38 ± 2.31 mg/dL). The study [70] showed that 97% of hemodialysis patients had insufficient levels of vitamin D3, indicating severe vitamin D3 deficiency. The work done by demonstrated the pivotal role of vitamin D in regulating calcium and phosphate balance in the human body [71]. PO4 levels have been shown to be significantly increased in patients with renal failure and another study has shown that PO4 is elevated in people with renal failure. [72]. The study [73] showed that the mean serum PO4 level was 6.2 ± 2.0 mg/dL.

Associations of parathyroid hormone (PTH), phosphate, and calcium (Ca) levels with mortality have been extensively studied among dialysis patients [74, 75]. many studies higher mortality of renal failure patients on dialysis were linked with lower calcium levels, higher phosphate, and high PTH level. Bone mineral disorder is a disorder of mineral and bone metabolism that most patients with chronic kidney disease suffer from [76]. There is a direct relationship between glomerular filtration rate and calcium, where the lower the level of Ca + 2 in the serum indicates a lower glomerular filtration rate. Vitamin D3 increases the ability to absorb calcium from the intestine. Since low vitamin D3 is an early feature of kidney disease, hypocalcemia is considered an expected outcome of chronic kidney disease [77].

An important complication of chronic kidney disease is anemia; it has many consequences and problems [78]. One of the most important symptoms observed in this current study is anemia, as there was a significant decrease in the concentration of hemoglobin (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV) in both males and females, platelets and iron levels compared to the healthy group. The results of other studies were consistent with the current study, as they showed a significant decrease among patients with renal failure compared to the healthy group. [79,80] The results showed the presence of anemia and low blood parameters in patients with renal failure compared to the healthy control group. (See figure 8)

Anemia is one of the complications in patients with renal failure and has a wide range of negative consequences including decreased kidney function, progression of chronic renal failure, increased cardiac output, left ventricular hypertrophy, angina, congestive heart failure, and decreased survival rates,[81] Anemia in patients with chronic renal failure has several causes. Low erythropoietin is the main cause of normal anemia in patients with chronic kidney disease. There are many other factors such as iron deficiency anemia (IDA), uremic toxins, acute infection, inflammation, blood loss during hemodialysis (HD), malnutrition, repeated blood sampling, and blood loss secondary to platelet

dysfunction, and also due to decreased iron absorption due to increased hepcidin levels. Other causes of anemia are folic acid and vitamin B12 deficiency [82]. Therefore, identifying risk factors and reducing modifiable factors may help prevent anemia and its negative outcomes in patients with chronic renal failure. This observation may be explained by decreased red blood cell formation, increased inflammation, functional iron deficiency, and decreased erythropoietin that occur with progressive loss of renal function in patients with advanced CKD ,[83] . CKD patients require frequent hospitalization with maintenance dialysis. Erythropoietin-stimulating agents (ESAs) are used to treat anemia in patients with CKD. Anemia is the most common complication in patients with CKD and is often called anemia of CKD. Chronic renal failure associated with anemia often results in increased morbidity and mortality in these patients. ,[84,85] Cases et al. have shown that most patients with CKD have normocytic anemia due to decreased red blood cell production secondary to defective erythropoietin secretion; another explanation is based on elevated serum urea levels, which may contain toxic substances that can inhibit normal red blood cell proliferation in the bone marrow, and another contributing factor is that increased aluminum in patients undergoing continuous hemodialysis also has an inhibitory effect on erythropoiesis.[86]

Anemia is a common complication in patients with renal failure. Severe anemia has been associated with an increased risk of bleeding, and the number of red blood cells (RBCs) is negatively correlated with bleeding time [87]. Notably, RBCs in the bloodstream not only alter the hemodynamic state, but also secrete substances that directly affect platelet function. By pushing platelets away from the axial flow and toward the vessel wall during normal laminar flow, RBCs in the center of the vessel promote interactions between platelets and the vessel wall [88]. Accordingly, correcting anemia appears to reduce the risk of bleeding, while stimulating hematopoiesis with erythropoietin increases platelet reactivity, thereby increasing the incidence of ischemic events. Ischemia is a lower-than-normal amount of blood flow to a part of the body [89,90,91].

Liver enzyme levels GOT,GPT and ALP in dialysis patients with CKD showed significant increases compared to healthy controls. These results are consistent with other studies that have shown increases in GOT, GOT, and ALP [92,93]. Elevated levels of GPT and GOT may serve as diagnostic markers for chronic renal failure (CRF) [94]. The researcher's findings [95] confirmed increased levels of ALP in the serum of renal failure patients. Other studies are consistent with the findings of this study. Research

confirms that ALP can help clinicians as a diagnostic marker in end-stage renal disease (ESRD) in at-risk patients [94,96].

In this study, a decrease in both total protein and albumin was observed in patients with CKD compared to the healthy control group. This result is consistent with another study [14]. Serum total protein levels are assessed as a test of kidney function. Conditions such as glomerulonephritis are associated with decreased TSP levels due to glomerular injury, which in turn impairs filtration leading to protein excretion in the urine. Protein excretion in the urine leads to decreased levels of protein in the bloodstream. A kidney condition associated with elevated TSP levels is nephritis. Both albumin and total protein levels are decreased in patients with hemodialysis and diabetes; this finding may be attributed to changes in the structure of the glomerular basement membrane, leading to leakage of albumin and some low-molecular-weight proteins, or to protein deficiency. This study is consistent with [97], which shows decreased albumin levels in hemodialysis patients. Albumin is the predominant protein in human plasma, accounting for approximately 50% of total serum protein concentration. The results of a recent study in the United States indicate that decreased ALB levels are strongly and independently associated with worsening kidney function [98]

The percentage of hepatitis B virus (HBV) was about 20% of the patients with renal failure undergoing hemodialysis (30 patients out of 150), hepatitis C virus (HCV) was 13% (20 out of 150), and there was a co-infection of HBV and HCV about 1.3% (2 out of 150). A study was conducted that compared the results of this study, where 29.3 % of dialysis patients were positive for hepatitis B virus [100], and there is another study that is consistent with the results of the study [101]. There is a study closed to the current study, where the incidence of hepatitis C virus infection in patients with chronic renal failure was about 11.7 [102] . A study consistent with the findings of this study reported a co-infection with both hepatitis B and hepatitis C of 0.8%[103]. Co-infection with both hepatitis B and hepatitis C has been reported from different studies ranging from 0.8% to 37%. [104]

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is an infectious disease affecting 391 million people, or 5% of the world's population, and is a major global public health concern [105]. According to the 2017 World Health Organization (WHO) Global Hepatitis Report, [106] 71 million people, or about 1% of the population, are living with hepatitis C virus (HCV) worldwide. Direct contact with blood, which often occurs during drug injection, sexual contact, needlestick injuries in healthcare settings, and inadequately sterilized medical equipment, are the main vectors for HSV transmission [107]. Although the incidence is less than 1 case per 2 million blood

transfusions, it can also be spread through blood transfusions [108]. In those undergoing hemodialysis, the most prevalent viruses are hepatitis B and C [109]. In contrast to the general population, hemodialysis patients are at increased risk of hepatitis B and C infections [110]. Patients are more likely to suffer from chronic liver inflammation and death as a result of hepatitis B (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) infections [111]. Infections with HBV and HCV are more likely to occur in patients with chronic renal illness because their immune systems are weaker. Patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) are more likely to have HBV and HCV infections than the general population due to their weakened immune systems and frequent blood transfusions [109].

Conclusion

This study showed a significant effect of various biochemical and hematological variables in chronic kidney disease and end-stage renal failure among men and women. There are viral liver infections among patients and research is needed to study the direct relationship between dialysis, liver enzymes, and hepatitis viruses and to study other types in this group of patients.

References

- [1] Kellum JA, Unruh ML, Murugan R. Acute kidney injury. *BMJ Clin Evid.* 2011;2011.
- [2] Bikbov B, Purcell CA, Levey AS, Smith M, Abdoli A, Abebe M, et al. Global, regional, and national burden of chronic kidney disease, 1990–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet.* 2020 Feb 29;395(10225):709-33. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30045-3.
- [3] Kalantar-Zadeh K, Jafar TH, Nitsch D, Neuen BL, Perkovic V. Chronic kidney disease. *Lancet.* 2021 Aug 28;398(10302):786-802. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00519-5.
- [4] Levey AS, Atkins R, Coresh J, Cohen EP, Collins AJ, Eckardt KU, et al. Chronic kidney disease as a global public health problem: approaches and initiatives—a position statement from Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes. *Kidney Int.* 2007 Aug;72(3):247-59. doi:10.1038/sj.ki.5002343.
- [5] Levin A, Ahmed SB, Carrero JJ, Foster B, Francis A, Hall RK, et al. Executive summary of the KDIGO 2024 Clinical Practice Guideline for the Evaluation and Management of Chronic Kidney Disease: known knowns and known unknowns. *Kidney Int.* 2024 Apr;105(4):684-701.
- [6] Chittinandana A, Chailimpamontree W, Chaloeiphap P. Prevalence of chronic kidney disease in Thai adult population. *J Med Assoc Thai.* 2006 Mar;89(Suppl 2).

- [7] Jager KJ, Kovesdy C, Langham R, Rosenberg M, Jha V, Zoccali C. A single number for advocacy and communication—worldwide more than 850 million individuals have kidney diseases. *Nephrol Dial Transplant.* 2019 Nov;34(11):1803-5. doi:10.1093/ndt/gfz174.
- [8] Dhaidan FA. Prevalence of end-stage renal disease and associated conditions in hemodialysis Iraqi patients. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2018 May;6(5):1515-8. doi:10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20181793.
- [9] Zhang L, Zhao MH, Zuo L, Wang Y, Yu F, Zhang H, et al. China kidney disease network (CK-NET) 2016 annual data report. *Kidney Int Suppl* (2011). 2020 Dec;10(2). doi:10.1016/j.kisu.2020.09.004.
- [10] Pal S. Primary causes of end-stage renal disease. *US Pharm.* 2016 Aug;41(8):6.
- [11] Elamin S, Abu-Aisha H. Prevention of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus transmission in hemodialysis centers: review of current international recommendations. *Arab J Nephrol Transplant.* 2011;4(1):35-47.
- [12] Almeras C, Argilés À. Progress in uremic toxin research: the general picture of uremia. *Semin Dial.* 2009 Jul;22(4):329-33. doi:10.1111/j.1525-139X.2009.00609.x.
- [13] Vanholder R, Gryp T, Glorieux G. Urea and chronic kidney disease: the comeback of the century? *Nephrol Dial Transplant.* 2018 Jan;33(1):4-12. doi:10.1093/ndt/gfx034.
- [14] Cheng T, Wang X, Han Y, Hao J, Hu H, Hao L. The level of serum albumin is associated with renal prognosis and renal function decline in patients with chronic kidney disease. *BMC Nephrol.* 2023 Mar;24(1):57. doi:10.1186/s12882-023-03072-y.
- [15] Mathaweasansurn A, Thongrod S, Khongkaew P, Phechkrajang CM, Wilairat P, Choengchan N. Simple and fast fabrication of microfluidic paper-based analytical device by contact stamping for multiple-point standard addition assay: application to direct analysis of urinary creatinine. *Talanta.* 2020 Apr;210:120675. doi:10.1016/j.talanta.2019.120675.
- [16] Galvão De Lima JJ, Américo da Fonseca J, Godoy AD. Baseline variables associated with early death and extended survival on dialysis. *Ren Fail.* 1998;20(4):581-7. doi:10.3109/08860229809045173.
- [17] Oksa H, Pasternack A, Pasanen M. Serum urea-creatinine ratio as a prognostic index in hemodialysis patients. *Clin Nephrol.* 1987 Mar;27(3):125-30.
- [18] Kumaravel S, Wu SH, Chen GZ, Huang ST, Lin CM, Lee YC, Chen CH. Development of ratiometric electrochemical molecular switches to assay endogenous formaldehyde in live cells, whole blood and creatinine in saliva. *Biosens Bioelectron.* 2021 Jan;171:112720. doi:10.1016/j.bios.2020.112720.
- [19] Li Y, Luo L, Nie M, Davenport A, Li Y, Li B, et al. A graphene nanoplatelet-polydopamine molecularly imprinted biosensor for ultratrace creatinine detection. *Biosens Bioelectron.* 2022 Nov;216:114638. doi:10.1016/j.bios.2022.114638.
- [20] Cánovas R, Cuartero M, Crespo GA. Modern creatinine (bio)sensing: challenges of point-of-care platforms. *Biosens Bioelectron.* 2019 Apr;130:110-24. doi:10.1016/j.bios.2019.01.048.
- [21] Ponnaiah SK, Prakash P. Carbon dots doped tungstic anhydride on graphene oxide nanoplates: a new picomolar-range creatinine selective enzymeless electrochemical sensor. *Mater Sci Eng C Mater Biol Appl.* 2020 Aug;113:111010. doi:10.1016/j.msec.2020.111010.
- [22] Rossing P. KDIGO 2020 clinical practice guideline for diabetes management in chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Int Suppl* (2011). 2020 Oct;98(4). doi:10.1016/j.kisu.2020.09.005.
- [23] Galindo RJ, Beck RW, Scioscia MF, Umpierrez GE, Tuttle KR. Glycemic monitoring and management in advanced chronic kidney disease. *Endocr Rev.* 2020 Oct;41(5):756-74. doi:10.1210/edrv/bnaa001.
- [24] Pasquel FJ, Tsegka K, Wang H, Cardona S, Galindo RJ, Fayfman M, et al. Clinical outcomes in patients with isolated or combined diabetic ketoacidosis and hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state: a retrospective, hospital-based cohort study. *Diabetes Care.* 2020 Feb;43(2):349-57. doi:10.2337/dc19-1169.
- [25] Ren L, Xiao X, Cai Y, Liu S, Gang X, Wang G. Clinical features and new perspectives on follow-up and treatment of secondary hyperparathyroidism in patients with chronic kidney disease.
- [26] Gronemeyer K, Fuss CT, Hermes F, Plass A, Koschker AC, Hannemann A, Völzke H, Hahner S. Renal complications in chronic hypoparathyroidism—a systematic cross-sectional assessment. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne).* 2023;14:1244647. doi:10.3389/fendo.2023.1244647.
- [27] Aramovna DZ, Islom I, Azizbek A, Zaxriddin S, Shohruh S, Dilorom O. Role of vitamin D in hyperparathyroidis. *J Sci Educ Cult Innov.* 2024;3(6):10-7.
- [28] Liu H, Zhao H, Zheng D, He W, Liu Y, Jin J, He Q, Lin B. Misdiagnosis of chronic kidney disease and parathyroid hormone testing during the past 16 years. *Sci Rep.* 2023;13(1):15838. doi:10.1038/s41598-023-43113-8.

- [29] Yuen NK, Ananthakrishnan S, Campbell MJ. Hyperparathyroidism of renal disease. *Perm J*. 2016;20(3).
- [30] Shiferaw WS, Akalu TY, Aynalem YA. Risk factors for anemia in patients with chronic renal failure: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ethiop J Health Sci*. 2020;30(5).
- [31] Kao CC, Wong HS, Wang YJ, Chou WH, Perwitasari DA, Wu MS, Chang WC. The role of genetic polymorphisms in STIM1 and ORAI1 for erythropoietin resistance in patients with renal failure. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2021;100(17). doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000025243.
- [32] Bargman JM, Skorecki K. Chronic kidney disease. In: *Harrison's principles of internal medicine*. 18th ed. 2015. p. 2308.
- [33] Botev R, Mallié JP. Reporting the eGFR and its implication for CKD diagnosis. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2008;3(6):1606-7. doi: 10.2215/CJN.02830608.
- [34] Perico N, Cattaneo D, Bikbov B, Remuzzi G. Hepatitis C infection and chronic renal diseases. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2009;4(1):207-20. doi: 10.2215/CJN.02830608.
- [35] Kovesdy CP, Ureche V, Lu JL, Kalantar-Zadeh K. Outcome predictability of serum alkaline phosphatase in men with pre-dialysis CKD. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 2010;25(9):3003-11. doi: 10.1093/ndt/gfq142.
- [36] Stanaway JD, Flaxman AD, Naghavi M, Fitzmaurice C, Vos T, Abubakar I, et al. The global burden of viral hepatitis from 1990 to 2013: findings from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2013. *Lancet*. 2016;388(10049):1081-8. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(16)30579-7.
- [37] Kato S, Chmielewski M, Honda H, Pecoits-Filho R, Matsuo S, Yuzawa Y, et al. Aspects of immune dysfunction in end-stage renal disease. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2008;3(5):1526-33. doi: 10.2215/CJN.00981107.
- [38] Eleftheriadis T, Kartsios C, Yiannaki E, Kazila P, Antoniadi G, Liakopoulos V, et al. Chronic inflammation and T cell zeta-chain downregulation in hemodialysis patients. *Am J Nephrol*. 2007;28(1):152-7. doi: 10.1159/000109082.
- [39] Ali N, Hussain W, Hayat A, Shah T, Wen R, Zeb I, et al. Prevalence and risk factors of hepatitis B and C viruses among haemodialysis patients: a multicentric study. *Eur J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2019;31(1):29-33. doi: 10.1097/MEG.0000000000001268.
- [40] Yoon JS, Lee HY, Chung SW, Kim SW, Chang Y, Lee YB, et al. Prognostic impact of concurrent nonalcoholic fatty liver disease in patients with chronic hepatitis B-related hepatocellular carcinoma. *J Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2020;35(11):1960-8. doi: 10.1111/jgh.15147.
- [41] Fabrizi F, Messa P. The epidemiology of HCV infection in patients with advanced CKD/ESRD: A global perspective. *Semin Dial*. 2019;32(2):93-8. doi: 10.1111/sdi.12774.
- [42] Okoro RN, Farate VT. The use of nephrotoxic drugs in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Int J Clin Pharm*. 2019;41:767-75. doi: 10.1007/s11096-019-00862-1.
- [43] Ezekiel UN, Joshua O, Ross SR, Phillip TB, Eunice OI. Prevalence and correlations of hepatorenal functions in diabetes and cardiovascular disease among stratified adults. *Acta Bio Med Atenei Parmensis*. 2019;90(1):97.
- [44] Damiati S. A pilot study to assess kidney functions and toxic dimethyl-arginines as risk biomarkers in women with low vitamin D levels. *J Med Biochem*. 2019;38(2):145. doi: 10.2478/jomb-2018-0024.
- [45] Rodríguez-Cubillo B, Carnero-Alcázar M, Cobiella-Carnicer J, Rodríguez-Moreno A, Alswies A, Velo-Plaza M, et al. Impact of postoperative acute kidney failure in long-term survival after heart valve surgery. *Interact Cardiovasc Thorac Surg*. 2019;29(1):35-42. doi: 10.1093/icvts/ivz053.
- [46] Vanholder R, Annemans L, Brown E, Gansevoort R, Gout-Zwart JJ, Lameire N, et al. Reducing the costs of chronic kidney disease while delivering quality health care: a call to action. *Nat Rev Nephrol*. 2017;13(7):393-409. doi: 10.1038/nrneph.2017.73.
- [47] Afriansya R, Sofyanita EN. Overview of ureum and creatinine levels in hemodialysis patients with chronic kidney disease. *Jaringan Lab Med*. 2020;2(1):6-11.
- [48] Pandya D, Nagrajappa AK, Ravi KS. Assessment and correlation of urea and creatinine levels in saliva and serum of patients with chronic kidney disease, diabetes and hypertension—a research study. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2016;10(10). doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2016/21440.8700.
- [49] Hamed SA. Neurologic conditions and disorders of uremic syndrome of chronic kidney disease: presentations, causes, and treatment strategies. *Expert Rev Clin Pharmacol*. 2019;12(1):61-90. doi: 10.1080/17512433.2019.1552214.
- [50] Lockwood MB, Dunn-Lopez K, Pauls H, Burke L, Shah SD, Saunders MA. If you build it, they may not come: modifiable barriers to patient portal use among pre-and post-kidney transplant patients. *JAMIA Open*. 2018;1(2):255-64. doi: 10.1093/jamiaopen/ooy024.

- [51] Shavit L, Lifschitz M, Galperin I. Influence of enteric nutrition on blood urea nitrogen (BUN) in very old patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). *Arch Gerontol Geriatr.* 2012 Jan;54(1):228-31. doi: 10.1016/j.archger.2011.03.001.
- [52] Abu Zeid SA, Asmaa M. A study of some physiological changes accompanying chronic renal failure and their negative effects on patients with renal failure. *J Coll Educ.* 2019;(14):.
- [53] Zhao L, Li S, Gao Y. Efficacy of statins on renal function in patients with chronic kidney disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Ren Fail.* 2021 Jan;43(1):718-28. doi: 10.1080/0886022X.2021.1915894.
- [54] Nirwan DS, Vyas RK, Jain S. Comparative study of serum urea, creatinine and C-reactive protein level in chronic kidney disease patients with healthy subjects. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2017 Apr;5(4):1480-3. doi: 10.18203/2320-6012.ijrms20171262.
- [55] Hassen HF, Al-Lami MQ, Al-Saedi AJ. Evaluation some biochemical levels in patients undergoing hemodialysis in Baghdad Governorate. *J Adv Lab Res Biol.* 2018;9(2):50-7.
- [56] De Rosa S, Greco M, Rauseo M, Annetta MG. The good, the bad, and the serum creatinine: exploring the effect of muscle mass and nutrition. *Blood Purif.* 2023 Nov;52(9-10):775-85. doi: 10.1159/000530506.
- [57] Hassab ZS, Merzah KS. Biochemical markers level in Iraqi renal failure patients on hemodialysis. *Age.* 2023 Jan;55(1.787):40-707.
- [58] Levey AS, De Jong PE, Coresh J, El Nahas M, Astor BC, Matsushita K, Gansevoort RT, Kasiske BL, Eckardt KU. The definition, classification, and prognosis of chronic kidney disease: a KDIGO Controversies Conference report. *Kidney Int.* 2011 Jul;80(1):17-28. doi: 10.1038/ki.2010.483.
- [59] Maeda M, Yabuki A, Suzuki S, Matsumoto M, Taniguchi K, Nishinakagawa H. Renal lesions in spontaneous insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus in the nonobese diabetic mouse: acute phase of diabetes. *Vet Pathol.* 2003 Mar;40(2):187-95. doi: 10.1354/vp.40-2-187.
- [60] Hostetter TH, Rennke HG, Brenner BM. The case for intrarenal hypertension in the initiation and progression of diabetic and other glomerulopathies. *Am J Med.* 1982 Mar;72(3):375-80. doi: 10.1016/0002-9343(82)90563-6.
- [61] Coward RJ, Welsh GI, Yang J, Tasman C, Lennon R, Koziell A, Satchell S, Holman GD, Kerjaschki D, Tavaré JM, Mathieson PW. The human glomerular podocyte is a novel target for insulin action. *Diabetes.* 2005 Nov;54(11):3095-102. doi: 10.2337/diabetes.54.11.3095.
- [62] Kumar S, Jha PR, Bavishi N, Pathak KJ. Study of evaluation and correlation of calcium and phosphorus in chronic kidney disease with reference to parathyroid hormone.
- [63] Salih SS, Yenzeel JH. Evaluation of thyroid hormones and some biochemical variables in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Iraqi J Sci.* 2020 May 28:985-92.
- [64] Al-jumaili RA, Al-Jumaili EF. Study of the causes of parathyroid hormone imbalance and some biochemical parameter in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Rom J Diabetes Nutr Metab Dis.* 2024 Jan;31(1):49-57. doi: 10.2478/rjdnmd-2024-0006.
- [65] Nwosu IF, Ibeson CE, Olawoye A, Kyaw H, Kumar K, Odigwe C, Nwosu CA, Oshunsanya A. Interpretation of parathyroid hormone levels in renal impairment. *Cureus.* 2022 Jun;14(6). doi: 10.7759/cureus.25601.
- [66] Balaky HM, Mustafa AJ, Ismail PA. Clinical significance of osteoprotegerin, vitamin D, obestatin and some biochemical variables in kidney failure patients. *Iraqi J Pharm Sci.* 2023 Jun;32(1):59-66.
- [67] Hruska KA, Sugatani T, Agapova O, Fang Y. The chronic kidney disease—mineral bone disorder (CKD-MBD): advances in pathophysiology. *Bone.* 2017 Jul;100:80-6. doi: 10.1016/j.bone.2016.11.013.
- [68] Meri MA, Al-Hakeem AH, Al-Abeadi RS, Mahdi DM. Study of the changes of some biochemical parameters of patients with renal failure. *Bull Natl Inst Health Sci.* 2022;140(3):2925-33.
- [69] Jouda J, Ibrahim RK, Herez MS. Vitamin D 3, parathyroid hormones, and calcium levels in patients with hypothyroidism and chronic kidney disease and the relationship between them. *EurAsian J Biosci.* 2020 Jan;14(1):.
- [70] González EA, Sachdeva A, Oliver DA, Martin KJ. Vitamin D insufficiency and deficiency in chronic kidney disease: a single center observational study. *Am J Nephrol.* 2004 Oct;24(5):503-10. doi: 10.1159/000081023.
- [71] Bouillon R. Extra-skeletal effects of vitamin D. *Vitamin D Clin Med.* 2018;50:72-88.
- [72] Eljamay SM, Saleh HA, Jumma AA. Correlation between calcium C+ and vitamin D and thyroid hormones PTH in patients with kidney failure. *Indones Annu Conf Ser.* 2024 Jul;.
- [73] Sk G. Association of elevated serum PO₄, Cax PO₄ product, and parathyroid hormone with cardiac mortality risk in chronic hemodialysis patients. *J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2001;12:2131-8.

- [74] Floege J, Kim J, Ireland E, Chazot C, Druke T, de Francisco A, Kronenberg F, Marcelli D, Passlick-Deetjen J, Scherthner G, Fouqueray B. Serum iPTH, calcium and phosphate, and the risk of mortality in a European haemodialysis population. *Nephrol Dial Transplant*. 2011 Jun;26(6):1948-55. doi: 10.1093/ndt/gfq219.
- [75] Block GA, Hulbert-Shearon TE, Levin NW, Port FK. Association of serum phosphorus and calcium x phosphate product with mortality risk in chronic hemodialysis patients: a national study. *Am J Kidney Dis*. 1998 Apr;31(4):607-17. doi: 10.1016/S0272-6386(98)70035-2.
- [76] Isakova T, Wahl P, Vargas G, Gutiérrez OM, Scialla J, Xie H, Appleby D, Nessel L, Bellovich K, Chen J, Hamm L. FGF23, PTH and phosphorus metabolism in the chronic renal insufficiency cohort. *Kidney Int*. 2011 Jun;79(12):1370-8. doi: 10.1038/ki.2011.47.
- [77] Janmaat CJ, Van Diepen M, Gasparini A, Evans M, Qureshi AR, Ärnlöv J, Barany P, Elinder CG, Rotmans JJ, Vervloet M, Dekker FW. Lower serum calcium is independently associated with CKD progression. *Sci Rep*. 2018 Mar 26;8(1):5148. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-23497-6.
- [78] Egbi OG, Okafor UH, Miebodei KE, Kasia BE, Kunle-Olowu OE, Unuigbo EI. Prevalence and correlates of chronic kidney disease among civil servants in Bayelsa state, Nigeria. *Niger J Clin Pract*. 2014 Oct 8;17(5):602-7. doi: 10.4103/1119-3077.141425.
- [79] Al Sharifi LM, Haddawi KH. Anemia and Iron Profile in Hemodialysis and Nonhemodialysis Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease. *J Appl Hematol*. 2024 Jul 1;15(3):192-6.
- [80] Abo Ghneim FD, Mohammed HJ, Al Koofee DA. Biochemical variations in patients with renal failure: A comparative study. *World Acad Sci J*. 2024 Nov 1;6(6):1-1.
- [81] Mikhail A, Brown C, Williams JA, Mathrani V, Shrivastava R, Evans J, Isaac H, Bhandari S. Renal association clinical practice guideline on Anaemia of Chronic Kidney Disease. *BMC Nephrol*. 2017 Dec;18(1):1-29. doi: 10.1186/s12882-017-0682-7.
- [82] Portolés J, Martín L, Broseta JJ, Cases A. Anemia in chronic kidney disease: from pathophysiology and current treatments, to future agents. *Front Med (Lausanne)*. 2021 Mar 26;8:642296. doi: 10.3389/fmed.2021.642296.
- [83] Yin P, Wu Q, Shou L, Dong X. Risk factors for anemia in patients with chronic kidney disease: a protocol for systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicine (Baltimore)*. 2021 Oct 8;100(40). doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000027371.
- [84] Mohammed MR, Mahmood B. Morphological Types of Anemia Associated with Chronic Renal Diseases. *Open Access Maced J Med Sci*. 2022 Apr 20;10(B):905-8. doi: 10.3889/oamjms.2022.9463.
- [85] Stauffer ME, Fan T. Prevalence of anemia in chronic kidney disease in the United States. *PLoS One*. 2014 Jan 2;9(1). doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0084943.
- [86] Cases A, Egocheaga MI, Tranche S, Pallarés V, Ojeda R, Górriz JL, Portolés JM. Anemia of chronic kidney disease: Protocol of study, management and referral to Nephrology. *Nefrología (Engl Ed)*. 2018 Jan 1;38(1):8-12. doi: 10.1016/j.nefro.2017.06.006.
- [87] Livio M, Marchesi D, Remuzzi G, Gotti E, Mecca G, De Gaetano G. Uraemic bleeding: role of anaemia and beneficial effect of red cell transfusions. *Lancet*. 1982 Nov 6;320(8306):1013-5. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(82)92253-7.
- [88] Turitto VT, Baumgartner HR. Platelet interaction with subendothelium in a perfusion system: physical role of red blood cells. *Microvasc Res*. 1975 May 1;9(3):335-44. doi: 10.1016/0026-2862(75)90063-6.
- [89] Singh AK, Szczech L, Tang KL, Barnhart H, Sapp S, Wolfson M, Reddan D. Correction of anemia with epoetin alfa in chronic kidney disease. *N Engl J Med*. 2006 Nov 16;355(20):2085-98. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa065485.
- [90] Toma C, Zahr F, Moguilanski D, Grate S, Semaan RW, Lemieux N, Lee JS, Cortese-Hassett A, Mulukutla S, Rao SV, Marroquin OC. Impact of anemia on platelet response to clopidogrel in patients undergoing percutaneous coronary stenting. *Am J Cardiol*. 2012 Apr 15;109(8):1148-53. doi: 10.1016/j.amjcard.2011.12.006.
- [91] Giustino G, Kirtane AJ, Baber U, Généreux P, Witzensichler B, Neumann FJ, Weisz G, Maehara A, Rinaldi MJ, Metzger C, Henry TD. Impact of anemia on platelet reactivity and ischemic and bleeding risk: from the assessment of dual antiplatelet therapy with drug-eluting stents study. *Am J Cardiol*. 2016 Jun 15;117(12):1877-83. doi: 10.1016/j.amjcard.2016.03.020.
- [92] Jassim MM. Assessment biochemical parameters and electrolyte in renal failure patients on hemodialysis and Type 2 diabetes patients in Tikrit city. *J Educ Sci Stud*. 2024;5(23).
- [93] Rogachev B, Ohayon S, Saad A, Vorobiovsky V, Gruenbaum BF, Leibowitz A, Boyko M, Shapira Y, Shnaider A, Zlotnik M, Azab AN. The effects of hemodialysis on blood glutamate levels in chronic renal failure: implementation for neuroprotection. *J Crit*

- Care. 2012 Dec 1;27(6):743.e1-7. doi: 10.1016/j.jcrc.2012.04.010.
- [94] Beddhu S, Ma X, Baird B, Cheung AK, Greene T. Serum alkaline phosphatase and mortality in African Americans with chronic kidney disease. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2009 Nov 1;4(11):1805-10. doi: 10.2215/CJN.00590109.
- [95] Taliencio JJ, Schold JD, Simon JF, Arrigain S, Tang A, Saab G, Nally JV Jr, Navaneethan SD. Prognostic importance of serum alkaline phosphatase in CKD stages 3-4 in a clinical population. *Am J Kidney Dis.* 2013 Oct 1;62(4):703-10. doi: 10.1053/j.ajkd.2013.04.016.
- [96] Shantouf R, Kovesdy CP, Kim Y, Ahmadi N, Luna A, Luna C, Rambod M, Nissenson AR, Budoff MJ, Kalantar-Zadeh K. Association of serum alkaline phosphatase with coronary artery calcification in maintenance hemodialysis patients. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol.* 2009 Jun 1;4(6):1106-14. doi: 10.2215/CJN.01100209.
- [97] Al-Rubaie HA, Hasan DD. Assessment of hematological and biochemical parameters in hemodialysis patients and the impact of hemodialysis duration on hepcidin, ferritin and CRP. *Iraq J Hematol.* 2014 Jul 1;3(2):85-97.
- [98] Lang J, Katz R, Ix JH, Gutierrez OM, Peralta CA, Parikh CR, Satterfield S, Petrovic S, Devarajan P, Bennett M, Fried LF. Association of serum albumin levels with kidney function decline and incident chronic kidney disease in elders. *Nephrol Dial Transplant.* 2018 Jun 1;33(6):986-92. doi: 10.1093/ndt/gfx269.
- [99] Habas Sr E, Eledrisi M, Khan F, Elzouki AN. Secondary hyperparathyroidism in chronic kidney disease: pathophysiology and management. *Cureus.* 2021 Jul;13(7). doi: 10.7759/cureus.16302.
- [100] Habas Sr E, Eledrisi M, Khan F, Elzouki AN. Secondary hyperparathyroidism in chronic kidney disease: pathophysiology and management. *Cureus.* 2021 Jul;13(7). doi: 10.7759/cureus.16392.
- [101] Salim RW, Abdullah BA. The prevalence of hepatitis B virus in high risk groups in Nineveh governorate/Iraq. *Baghdad Sci J.* 2014 Jun;11(2):888-93. doi: 10.22401/BSJ.11.2.11.
- [102] Lodhi A, Sajjad A, Mehmood K, Lodhi A, Rizwan S, Ubaid A, Baloch K, Ahmed S, Mehmood Z. Profile and predictors of hepatitis and HIV infection in patients on hemodialysis of Quetta, Pakistan. *Drug Discov Ther.* 2019 Oct 31;13(5):274-9. doi: 10.5582/ddt.2019.03019.
- [103] Al-Mashhadani JI. Hepatitis C virus infection among haemodialysis patients in Al-Anbar governorate. *Iraqi J Community Med.* 2007;20(1):20-3.
- [104] Malhotra R, Sooin D, Grover P, Galhotra S, Khutan H, Kaur N. Hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus co-infection in hemodialysis patients: A retrospective study from a tertiary care hospital of North India. *J Nat Sci Biol Med.* 2016 Jan;7(1):72-6. doi: 10.4103/0976-9668.179089.
- [105] Jain P, Nijhawan S. Occult hepatitis C virus infection is more common than hepatitis B infection in maintenance hemodialysis patients. *World J Gastroenterol.* 2008 Apr 4;14(14):2288-92. doi: 10.3748/wjg.14.2288.
- [106] James SL, Abate D, Abate KH, Abay SM, Abbafati C, Abbasi N, Abbastabar H, Abd-Allah F, Abdela J, Abdelalim A, Abdollahpour I. Global, regional, and national incidence, prevalence, and years lived with disability for 354 diseases and injuries for 195 countries and territories, 1990–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet.* 2018 Nov 17;392(10159):1789-858. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32279-7.
- [107] World Health Organization. Global hepatitis report 2017. World Health Organization; 2017. Available from: WHO report.
- [108] Banday D, Rather B, Parrey A. Comparison between complications of hepatitis C treatment in patients with malignancy and those without malignancy. *Int J.* 2021 May;4(3):883-91. doi: 10.1007/s42175-021-00211-x.
- [109] Fong IW. Blood transfusion-associated infections in the twenty-first century: new challenges. *Curr Trends Infect Dis.* 2020:191-215. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-820578-4.00014-0.
- [110] Adane T, Getawa S. The prevalence and associated factors of hepatitis B and C virus in hemodialysis patients in Africa: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2021 Jun 22;16(6). doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0251570.
- [111] Alashek WA, McIntyre CW, Taal MW. Hepatitis B and C infection in haemodialysis patients in Libya: prevalence, incidence and risk factors. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2012 Dec;12:1-8. doi: 10.1186/1471-2334-12-127.

